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Effect of Strontium Segregation on Electrochemical Impedance Spectra for $\text{La}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ Cathodes

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Abstract

Microtubular solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) with $\text{La}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (LSCF) cathodes were aged in ambient air at temperatures ranging from 700 to 1000 °C for up to 700 h. The amount of segregated Sr, present both on LSCF surfaces and in Sr-rich particles, increased with increasing aging temperature. Distribution of relaxation times (DRT) analysis of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements indicated an increase in the cathode resistance with increasing aging temperature up to 900 °C. Analysis of microstructural data, which were collected with focused ion beam-scanning electron microscopy (FIB-SEM) 3D tomography, and the EIS data using the Alder-Lane-Steele (ALS) model indicates that the Sr surface segregation increases cathode resistance via a decreased oxygen surface exchange coefficient.

Introduction

$\text{La}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (LSCF) is widely used as a cathode material for solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs). However, LSCF can be susceptible to degradation by mechanisms including reactions with yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ) electrolytes [1], Cr poisoning from steel stack components [2-4], microstructural coarsening [5,6] and Sr surface segregation [7]. Coarsening and sintering of porous electrodes are expected at sufficiently high temperatures, long times, and small particle sizes. However, it is difficult to predict whether a given electrode will be susceptible to coarsening/sintering because of the strong dependence of coarsening rate on initial feature size. For example, coarsening of initially ~ 50-nm-diameter infiltrated LSCF to > 100 nm after aging for ~ 1000 h at ≥ 700 °C has been shown to measurably increase polarization resistance [5,6]. On the other hand, no coarsening was observed for LSCF with larger feature sizes of ~300 nm particle size aged for ~ 1000 h at up to 800 °C [7] or for LSCF with 550 nm feature size aged for 1000 h at 600 – 900 °C [8]. In the latter study, an increase in polarization resistance was observed after aging at 600 and 750 °C, despite no change in microstructure [8]; this may have been due to Sr segregation, which was not tested in that study.

Here, we present results on LSCF cathodes on microtubular SOFCs with aging at 700 – 1000 °C for up to 700 h. The cells utilize $\text{Ce}_{0.9}\text{Gd}_{0.1}\text{O}_{1.95}$ (GDC) electrolytes, so there is no issue with LSCF/YSZ reactions. Silver paste and wire were used as current collectors in order to avoid Cr poisoning and thereby focus on the effects of coarsening/sintering and Sr segregation with focused ion beam-scanning electron microscopy (FIB-SEM) 3D tomography. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) data taken before and after aging under various conditions is analyzed using distribution of relaxation times (DRT) methods to isolate the cathode polarization resistance.

1. Experiments

Anode microtubes were composed of 60 wt.% NiO (Sumitomo Metal Mining)-40 wt.% GDC (Anan Kasei). The anode microtubes were extruded with pore former (acrylic resin with 5 μm in grain size; Sekisui Plastic) and binder (Cellulose; Yuken Kogyo) powders. The GDC electrolyte was formed by dip-coating using a slurry with a binder (polyvinyl butyral; Sekisui Chemical), a dispersant (tallow propylene diamine; Kao) and a plasticizer (dioctyl adipate; Wako Pure Chemical Industries) in ethanol and toluene solvents. The GDC thin-film electrolyte (5 μm in thickness) and NiO anode microtube (200 μm) were co-sintered in air for 3 h at 1450 °C. Then, the LSCF (Kusaka Rare Metal) thin-film cathode (20 μm) was coated and sintered in air for 1 h at 1050 °C. The outside diameter of microtube was 1.8 mm, and the cathode length was 10 mm after sintering. The microtubular cells were aged at 700, 800, 900 and 1000 °C in a tube furnace exposed to ambient air. Two aging times, 300 and 700 h, were used at each temperature. An as-prepared cell was used as a reference “control” sample, for comparison with the aged cells.

In preparation for 3D tomography, the pores within the LSCF cathodes were infiltrated with a low-viscosity epoxy prior to the observation. The serial sectioning and imaging were carried out using a FEI Helios system with 2 kV electron beam energy and backscattered electron (BSE) detector. The image resolution was 15 × 15 nm and the spacing between images was 30 nm. The imaged area was located close to the cathode/electrolyte interface and the milling direction was perpendicular to the tube axis. For Sr surface segregation measurements, the cell fragments were separately stirred in ultrapure H_2O for 10 min after cutting with a diamond saw. Subsequently, the samples were transferred into a 12 mol·L⁻¹ HCl solution and stirred until the cathodes were completely dissolved. The tubes with ultrapure H_2O solution were then centrifuged and

only the upper part of the solution was used, in order to eliminate any loose particles. The ultrapure H₂O and the concentrated HCl solutions were mixed with the appropriate amounts of H₂O/HCl/HNO₃ to yield 0.36 mol·L⁻¹ HCl/0.72 mol·L⁻¹ HNO₃ solutions for inductivity coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometer (ICP-OES) analysis.

EIS measurement was performed with a potentiostat/galvanostat and an impedance analyzer (Bio-Logic Science Instruments VSP) at open circuit voltage (OCV) in the frequency range from 1 MHz to 0.1 Hz with 20 steps per logarithmic decade. The operating temperature was 550 °C. A mixture of H₂ : H₂O : N₂ = 20 : 3 : 77 was supplied as fuel at a flow rate of 100 mL/min to the anode side, and a mixture of O₂ : N₂ = 21 : 79 was supplied as oxidant at 100 mL/min to the cathode side. DRT analysis was done as described in Refs. [9-12]. The software package FTIKREG [13] was used to solve an ill-posed inverse problem in DRT analysis by Tikhonov regularization.

2. Results and Discussion

Figure 1 presents 2D FIB-SEM cross-sectional images from the control and aged LSCF electrodes. Only the 700 h aged samples are shown here, since the 300 h aged samples have similar structure. The lighter contrast particles are identified as LSCF, whereas the darker contrast indicates pore. It can be clearly seen that the LSCF particles of the sample aged at 1000 °C for 700 h have significantly larger size relative to the others, indicating substantial coarsening of LSCF at this temperature. Regions with intermediate grey contrast, indicated by white arrows, are apparent in the 800C-700h and 900C-700h images, suggesting that another phase is present. These are not seen in the 700C-700h image. EDS element mapping, conducted on the area indicated in Fig. 1 (d) and shown in Fig. 1 (f), shows that the third phase contains primarily Sr.

Fig. 1 SEM images of the (a) control, (b) 700C-700h, (c) 800C-700h, (d) 900C-700h and (e) 1000C-700h aged LSCF electrodes. (f) EDS element mapping of the boxed area shown in (d).

The macrohomogeneous microstructural parameters obtained from the 3D image data are summarized and plotted in Fig. 2. The porosity varied between 36 and 43% for all cathodes; while this variation is slightly greater than the 5% accuracy, it is difficult to establish any meaningful trend. Tortuosity values followed the trend expected, i.e., decreasing with increasing phase volume fraction. Thus, tortuosity was lower, ~ 1.1 , for LSCF ($\sim 60\%$ volume fraction) compared to ~ 1.2 for the pore phase ($\sim 40\%$ volume fraction). The LSCF specific surface area decreased by $> 30\%$ for 1000C-300h and 1000C-700h samples, respectively, indicating LSCF coarsening likely occurred under these aging conditions. Although there appears to also be smaller decreases in specific surface area with increasing aging temperature below 1000 °C, at least for the 700 h case, it is difficult to be sure of this trend given experimental errors. LSCF particles grew measurably only after aging at the highest temperature, 1000 °C, and further increased in size with increasing aging time from 300 to 700 h. The 900C-700h sample did not show change in average particle size relative to the control sample, but had slightly increased volume fraction at ~ 1150 nm. Again, these large particles are likely due to treating Sr-rich phase as LSCF particles during segmentation. Based on the above results, it can be concluded that the LSCF did not coarsen significantly at ≤ 900 °C, consistent with the surface area results in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 (a) Porosity, (b) pore and LSCF phase tortuosity, (c) LSCF specific surface area, versus temperature for cells aged for 300 and 700h, and (d) LSCF particle size distributions determined from measured 3D structural data.

Figure 3 (a) shows the amount of Sr dissolved in ultrapure water for the control and aged cells, detected by ICP-OES, normalized to the measured electrode volume. Previous results show that only Sr-rich surface layers or phases are water-soluble, while the bulk LSCF is insoluble in water [7], so the detected Sr amount can be used as a measure of the total amount of surface segregated Sr and the Sr-rich phase. The amount of Sr increased with increasing aging time and temperature up to 900 °C, from $0.28 \pm 0.03 \times 10^5$ nmol/cm³ for the control sample to $1.28 \pm 0.17 \times 10^5$ nmol/cm³ for the 900C-700h sample. However, increasing the aging temperature from 900 to 1000 °C resulted in much smaller surface Sr amount, $0.45 \pm 0.02 \times 10^5$ nmol/cm³ for the 300 h sample and $0.52 \pm 0.02 \times 10^5$ nmol/cm³ for the 700 h sample. It is plausible that this high aging temperature suppresses the Sr surface segregation, an explanation that is consistent with the low surface Sr amount observed for the control sample, which was fired at 1050 °C. It is estimated that most of the Sr detected was segregated on LSCF surfaces, versus in Sr-rich particles. Using this and assuming that the segregated phase is a dense homogeneous SrO coverage with a (100) orientation, the nominal SrO monolayer (ML) coverage increases from ~ 0.8 ML for the control sample up to ~ 3.5 ML for 900C-700h sample, but decreases to ~ 1.9 ML for 1000C-700h sample (Fig. 3 (b)).

Fig. 3 (a) The amount of Sr dissolved in ultrapure water for the control and aged cells normalized to the measured electrode volume. (b) The corresponding nominal number of SrO monolayers estimated assuming dense homogeneous SrO coverage with a (100) orientation. The error bars were calculated from standard deviation of 3 measurements.

Figure 4 (a) shows the impedance spectra for the control and aged microtubular cells measured between the anode and cathode under OCV at 550 °C. The ohmic loss for the aged samples was slightly larger than that for the control sample. There was a substantial increase in the polarization resistance after aging that increased with increasing aging temperature. DRT analysis was applied to this impedance data to separate each response – the results are shown in Fig. 4 (b). Three large peaks were detected at 0.1 – 100 Hz by the DRT analysis for all samples. The small DRT peak around 1 kHz (P_1^a) was ascribed to the fuel oxidation process on the anode for microtubular cells [11]. On the other hand, we confirmed by another experiment that the DRT peak around 7 Hz (P_1^d) increased with decreasing hydrogen concentration in the anode [11]. This peak is ascribed to gas diffusion process for anode-supported cells. After aging, the DRT peak around 1 Hz (P_2^d) appeared. This peak is also related to gas diffusion with consideration of frequency. Thus, the increase in impedance at ~ 1 Hz is presumably caused by a change in the anode morphology during aging.

The peak around 100 Hz (P_2^c) was ascribed to the oxygen reduction reaction on the LSCF electrode [12]. In this study, we focus on the chemical resistance R_{chem} and time constant t_{chem} of P_2^c . Prior studies in the literature have shown that the impedance of porous mixed-conducting cathodes with fast electronic transport, such as LSCF, is co-

Fig. 4 (a) Impedance and (b) DRT spectra for the control and aged microtubular cells measured between the anode and cathode under OCV at 550 °C.

limited by the oxygen surface exchange and solid-state oxygen ion diffusion processes, and can be expressed as described in [14]:

$$Z_G = \frac{R_{chem}}{\sqrt{1 + j\omega t_{chem}}} \quad (1)$$

where j is the imaginary unit. Figure 5 shows the R_{chem} and t_{chem} of P_2^c derived by fitting as a Gerischer impedance Z_G . Both R_{chem} and t_{chem} increased after aging. The values of R_{chem} for the samples aged at 900 °C were larger than those at 700 and 800 °C, while the values of t_{chem} was independent on the aging temperature from 700 to 900 °C.

Fig. 5 (a) Chemical resistance R_{chem} and (b) time constant t_{chem} of P_2^c for the control and aged microtubular cells.

Based on the electrochemical and microstructural data, Adler-Lane-Steele (ALS) model was applied to examine the effect of aging on the oxygen reduction reaction [15]. The values of R_{chem} and t_{chem} are related to the microstructural, thermodynamic and kinetic properties of the electrode:

$$R_{\text{chem}} = \frac{RT}{4F^2} \left(\frac{\tau A_0^2}{4a(1-\varepsilon)k_{\text{chem}}D_{\text{chem}}c^2\chi} \right)^{1/2} (p_{\text{O}_2})^{-1/4} \quad (2)$$

$$t_{\text{chem}} = \frac{(1-\varepsilon)\chi}{4ak_{\text{chem}}} (p_{\text{O}_2})^{-1/2} \quad (3)$$

where porosity ε , LSCF tortuosity τ , and specific surface area a are given in Fig. 2. The oxygen lattice site concentration c , oxygen vacancy fraction χ , and thermodynamic enhancement factor A_0 for this LSCF composition at operating temperature of 550 °C are found in the literature to be 0.083 mol/cm³, 0.0037, and 1.11, respectively [16-18]. With the values of these parameters known, and R_{chem} and t_{chem} values obtained from the DRT analysis, the oxygen surface exchange coefficient k_{chem} and oxygen diffusion coefficient D_{chem} were obtained, and are shown in Fig. 6. While k_{chem} and D_{chem} are chemical coefficients, prior measurements of LSCF at 550 °C were done by isotope exchange depth profiling (IEDP) coupled with secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS), which yields the tracer coefficients $k^* = 5.51 \times 10^{-8} - 1.40 \times 10^{-7}$ cm/s and $D^* = 3.47 \times 10^{-11} - 4.58 \times 10^{-11}$ cm²/s [19,20]. Conversion of these to chemical coefficients using the expressions $k_{\text{chem}} = (A_0 / \chi) k^*$ and $D_{\text{chem}} = (A_0 / \chi) D^*$ [18] yields $k_{\text{chem}} = 1.65 \times 10^{-5} - 4.19 \times 10^{-5}$ cm/s and $D_{\text{chem}} = 1.05 \times 10^{-8} - 1.38 \times 10^{-8}$ cm²/s. The present k_{chem} values are in good agreement. The present D_{chem} values are 5 – 10 times lower, possibly due to differences between the dense LSCF samples used in IEDP/SIMS and the present porous LSCF electrodes. The k_{chem} values after aging are substantially lower than for the control sample, indicating that the Sr surface segregation inhibited the oxygen surface exchange. However, there is no clear trend in k_{chem} between 700, 800 and 900 °C aging temperatures. Although increase in Sr surface segregation with temperature and time has been observed by ICP-OES measurement, it cannot be directly associated with the change in k_{chem} , as the measurement cannot distinguish between a uniform coverage of the LSCF surface and Sr-rich 3D islands. The isolated 3D islands, which were observed for samples aged at 800 and 900 °C, are expected to have little impact on k_{chem} . On the other hand, we believe that the variations in D_{chem} between the control sample and those aged at 700-800 °C results from the combined error of the 3D tomography data, the EIS measurement, and the DRT analysis. That is, Sr surface segregation has relatively small impact on the oxygen diffusion process below 900 °C. However, D_{chem} decreases with aging time for samples aged at 900 °C. This might be due to a change in the LSCF composition resulting from Sr surface segregation, giving a slightly increased La/Sr ratio. Comparison with Fig. 5 shows that the R_{chem} increase after aging at 700 – 800 °C was mainly due to the decrease in k_{chem} , whereas the further increase at 900 °C was due to the decrease in D_{chem} .

Fig. 6 (a) Surface exchange k_{chem} and (b) oxygen diffusion coefficients D_{chem} for the control and aged microtubular cells.

4. Conclusion

Microtubular SOFCs with LSCF cathodes were aged at elevated temperatures ranging from 700 to 1000 °C, for 300 and 700 h. 3D tomographic measurements done by FIB-SEM serial sectioning indicated that the LSCF surface area did not decrease significantly until aging temperatures were increased above 900 °C. Sr surface segregation, measured by a chemical etching technique, increased with increasing aging temperature up to 900 °C, but decreased with further increase in temperature to 1000 °C. The segregated Sr was present mainly as a thin layer covering LSCF surfaces, with a smaller amount present as Sr-rich particles. EIS measurements with DRT analysis revealed a response associated with co-limiting oxygen surface exchange and oxygen diffusion processes in the LSCF cathode. The chemical resistance and time constant associated with this response increased after aging. The EIS data, analyzed using the ALS model together with measured microstructural data, indicate that aging under any condition decreases the oxygen surface exchange coefficient by a factor of ~ 2 , whereas the oxygen diffusion coefficient decreased only for 900 °C aging. Thus, Sr surface segregation appears to be the primary mechanism causing degradation of LSCF electrodes.

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